

SOCIAL NETWORKS AS A FACTOR IN THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL RELATIONS OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract: The social activity of young people differs in its characteristics from the social activity of other layers of society. This is primarily due to the incomplete formation of the position of young people in society. Young people experience the process of entering social structures, that is, socialization. Social activity of young people has its own characteristics in each field of social activity. Based on this, it should be studied in several directions: economic education, social protection, spiritual and moral life. It is possible to understand the movement to add, not to lag behind the times

Key words: youth, knowledge, social, active, psychological, consciousness, individual, community development, skills.

Social networks can provide a platform for young people to connect with peers, share experiences, and build communities based on shared interests. It can help them maintain relationships, explore diverse perspectives, and develop social skills. Social media lets teens create online identities, chat with others and build social networks. These networks can provide teens with support from other people who have hobbies or experiences in common. This type of support especially may help teens who: Lack social support offline or are lonely.

Youth activity refers to the characteristics of the manifestation of its internal and external tendencies in social life. Social activity is the main expression of the level of a person as a person, satisfaction of his high-value needs and quality indicator. So, social activity is an important quality of a person. It is said that youth activism is related to the management of his life and the characteristics of his values. Social activity is the main expression of the level of the quality of the human personality, it is a way to satisfy his high-value needs and a quality indicator. In this respect, individual activity is studied in sociology at broad and small (narrow) social levels. The study of the personality at such levels acquires methodological importance.

The process of changes and fundamental reforms taking place in the life of our society today requires social activity from non-governmental non-commercial organizations and public associations, which are defined as institutions of civil society. So what is social activism? Social activity can be understood as the effort of a person to contribute to the development of society and not fall behind the times, regardless of the occupation or position of a

person. In this process, he shows himself as a person and a citizen. Today we see that our compatriots are becoming socially active. The period of social depression, indifference to changes and reforms has passed, and we are witnessing initiative and striving for innovation among our compatriots. There are also opinions on the content that "social networks have increased social activity".

Civil activism can be evaluated as a creative approach to socio-political and labor activities. It is the civic activity of a person that serves the full development of a person and the full manifestation of his potential. Having a civic position and civic activity requires a deep understanding of all the events taking place in society, their consequences and solutions to existing problems. Therefore, we must form civic consciousness in our youth. Civic consciousness serves to unite society, in the direction of common interests. Serves to make an agreement between citizens. Under the influence of various sociocultural factors occurring in society, civic consciousness changes and is reflected in the development of ideas about citizenship. The more developed the civic consciousness of young people, the more active their social activity in society.

In the process of analyzing this article, the methods of logicity, historicity, consistency and objectivity of scientific knowledge were widely used. An analysis of the state of social activity among young people and forms of implementation was carried out. Tursunova N.'s educational manual entitled "Social activity of young people: concepts and qualities" was designated as a methodological source. It is the dream of every Uzbek to see our independent country among the developed countries. But this dream did not appear yesterday or today. The strong democratic reforms initiated by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev undoubtedly gave impetus to the increase of this desire in the hearts of our compatriots, to the strengthening of the desire to build a new Uzbekistan, and to the increase in social activity, which we have already mentioned.

Today, Uzbekistan has taken a step from national recovery to national growth. Everyone wants the reforms aimed at development and prosperity to be effective. The reason is that as a result of such reforms, the people will live well. The sense of belonging to reforms and changes encourages a person to be socially active.

In conclusion, the continuous organization of a specific activity creates certain skills in a person. And skills become competencies in the process of consistent continuation of activities. The formed qualification ensures a quick, high-quality,

and efficient performance of the activity by the individual. To the extent that humanity has been interested in achieving efficiency in activity, the professional qualification of the person organizing it has gained such relevance. Acquiring a professional qualification has social as well as personal significance.

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